

**YONG‘IN SHAROITIDA QURILISH MATERIALLARIDA SODIR BO‘LADIGAN
ASOSIY HOSSALAR VA JARAYONLAR**

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Mexanik xossalar. Egilishga mustahkamlik chegarasini aniqlash

$$R_{eg} = \frac{3 \cdot P_{buz} \cdot L}{2 \cdot b \cdot h^2}, \text{ MPa}$$

bu yerda; R_{buz} , P_{buz} - namunaga qo‘yilgan yuk, kg

L - tayanchlar orasidagi masofa, sm

b - namuna ko‘ndalang kesimining eni, sm

h^2 - namuna ko‘ndalang kesimining balandligi, sm

Misol: 1200 g gips olinadi suvga solinadi, 60 sekund davomida aralashtirilib moylangan qolipga solinadi. 2 soatdan so‘ng 4x4x16 sm o‘lchamli namuna MII-100 qurilmasiga qo‘yilib egilishga bo‘lgan mustahkamligi topiladi. 2ta pastki tayanch orasidagi masofa 100 mm. Egilishga mustahkamlik chegarasi, kgs/sm MPa

$$R_{eg} = \frac{3 \cdot P_{buz} \cdot L}{2 \cdot b \cdot h^2} = \frac{3 \cdot 180 \cdot 16}{2 \cdot 4 \cdot 4^2} = 67,5 \text{ MPa}$$

Siqilishga bo‘lgan mustahkamlik chegarasini aniqlash.

$$R_{siq} = \frac{R_{buz}}{F}$$

Misol: Siqilishga bo‘lgan mustahkamlik chegarasini aniqlash uchun 6 ta yarimta balkachalardan foydalanamiz. Yarim balkachalarning tepa va pastki qismiga o‘lchamlari 40x62,5 mm keladigan yani yuzasi 25 sm² bo‘lgan po‘lat listlar qo‘yiladi va gidravlik press yordamida siqilishga bo‘lgan mustahkamlik chegarasi aniqlanadi. Siqilishga mustahkamlik chegarasi, kgs/sm MPa

$$R_{siq} = \frac{R_{buz}}{F} = \frac{10000}{25} = 400 \text{ kgs/sm MPa}$$

Cho‘zilishga bo‘lgan mustahkamlik chegarasini aniqlash.

$$R_{cho'z} = \frac{l_k - l_0}{l_0}$$

bu yerda: l_k - cho‘zilgandan keyingi uzunligi; l_0 - cho‘zilishdan oldingi uzunligi

Misol: Po‘lat armaturani cho‘zilishga mustaxkamligini aniqlaymiz. Berilgan: Po‘lat namunasini cho‘zilishdan oldingi uzunligi 25 sm, cho‘zilgandan keyingi uzunligi 27 sm,

Yechish:

$$R_{cho'z} = \frac{l_k - l_0}{l_0} = \frac{27 - 25}{25} = 0.08sm$$

Ayrim materiallarning vaqtinchalik qarshilik ko‘rsatishining sonli qiymati

Material	Vaqtinchalik qarshilik ko‘rsatishi R, MPa		
	R_{siq}	$R_{cho'z}$	R_{eg}
1. Torf plitalar	0,5	-	0,25- 0,2
2. Oddiy betonlar	5-30	0,6- 2,0	-
3. Yuqori sifatli beton	40-80	2,5- 7,0	-
4. Xom g‘isht	7,5-30	-	1,5- 3,5
5. Yog‘och: tolalariga ko‘ndalang, tolalari bo‘ylab	50 6,5	130 6,5	100 75
6. Shishaplastik	420	450- 470	410- 460
7. Granit	100- 250	2-4,4	-
8. Po‘lat	380- 450	380- 450	-

Deformativlik – absolyut, nisbiy deformatsiya hajmi bo‘yicha material namunasining massasini o‘zgartirmagan holda o‘lchamlarini (shaklini) o‘zgartirish xususiyatidir. Namunalar (buyumlar) ning deformatsiyalanishi siqilishda, cho‘zilishda, surilish, egilishda va boshqa hollarda sodir bo‘ladi.

Egiluvchanlik – ta’sir etayotgan kuch natijasida material namunalarining o‘z shaklini o‘zgartirishi va kuch olingandan so‘ng boshlang‘ich shakliga qaytish xususiyatidir.

Oquvchanlik chegarasi (σ_y)- plastik deformatsiyalar o'sishiga olib keluvchi doimiy kuchlanish

Egiluvchanlik darajasi (σ_y) – materialda qoldiq deformatsiya hosil qilmaydigan maksimal kuchlanish. Materialning deformativ mustahkamlik xarakteristikalarini kuchlanish diagrammasi ifodalaydi. Materialning egilishdagi deformatsiyasi *Guk qonuniga* asosan to'g'ri burchakli kuchlanishlar diagrammasidagi maksimal kuchlanish.

$$\sigma = E\varepsilon ,$$

bu yerda; ε - nisbiy deformatsiya bo'lib, cho'zilishda quyidagi formula bilan aniqlanadi.

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\lambda_1 - \lambda_0}{\lambda_0} ,$$

bu yerda; λ_0 - namunaning cho'zilishgacha bo'lgan uzunligi, m; λ_1 - namunaning cho'zilishdan keyingi uzunligi, m; E - elastiklik (egiluvchanlik) moduli, Pa.

Plastiklik- yuk ta'sirida material namunasining buzilmasdan o'z shaklini o'zgartirishi va yuk olingandan so'ng o'zining yangi shaklini saqlab qolish xususiyati. Materiallarning bu xossasi *oquvchanlik* bilan xarakterlanadi.

Qattqlik – materialga nisbatan ancha qattiq materialning qarshilik ko'rsatish xususiyatidir. Metallar uchun qattqlik darajasi Brenell qiymati bo'yicha (HB) aniqlanadi. Tabiiy tosh materiallarining qattqligi qattqlik shkalasi bo'yicha aniqlaniladi.

Moos qattqlik shkalasi

Minerallar	Kimyoviy tarkibi	Qattqlik ko'rsatkichi
Talk	$Mg_3(OH)_2 \cdot Si_2O_5$	1
Gips	$CaSO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$	2
Kalsiy	$CaCO_3$	3
Eruvchan shisha	CaF_2	4
Apatit	$Ca_5(PO_4)_3 \cdot FCl Ca_5$	5
Ortoklaz	$K(Al \cdot SiO_3 \cdot O_8)$	6
Kvars	SiO_2	7
Topaz	$Al(F \cdot OH) \cdot SiO_2$	8
Korund	Al_2O_3	9

Olmos	S	10
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Shkalada maxsus saralab olingan minerallar shunday ketma-ketlikda joylashtiriladiki, bunda tartib bo'yicha navbatdagi material o'zidan oldingi materialda chiziq qoldiradi, o'zi esa yemirilmaydi.

	Tabiiy holatda		Absolyut holatda		G'ovaklik		Gigroskopi k		Egilishga				Siqilishga		Chuzilis hga	
	m	V	m	V	P	P ₀	m ₁	m	p _{bus}	L	b	h	R _{buz}	F	l _k	l _o
1	740	1.1	1500	1.1	2000	3500	333	110	185	11	3	4	1890	15	25	12
2	735	1.2	2600	1.2	2400	3100	444	122	195	13	4	2	1900	19	29	15
3	725	1.3	2200	1.3	2600	3300	555	135	200	15	2	3	2001	18	30	17
4	743	1.4	2300	1.4	2650	3500	666	145	201	19	3	4	2011	17	33	20
5	770	1.5	2220	1.5	2780	3600	777	155	174	18	4	5	1000	11	41	22
6	750	1.6	2650	1.6	2800	3700	888	175	186	17	5	6	1250	13	44	26
7	743	1.7	2700	1.7	2850	4000	999	300	185	11	6	7	1850	19	27	12
8	730	1.8	2750	1.8	2855	2855	540	300	174	13	7	8	1950	20	26	15
9	725	1.9	2800	1.9	1800	2900	545	250	45	19	8	9	1000	21	25	19
10	738	2.1	2900	2.1	1750	3050	450	150	144	20	9	3	1200	23	27	17
11	741	2.2	3000	2.2	1890	3055	444	145	122	21	3	4	1212	25	28	16
12	750	2.3	3500	2.3	1900	2950	750	450	123	23	4	2	1235	29	29	20
13	751	2.4	3100	2.4	2001	3330	486	230	110	25	2	3	1239	30	30	21
14	760	2.5	3300	2.5	2011	3350	444	290	122	29	3	4	1359	33	31	22
15	765	2.6	3500	2.6	1000	3800	564	320	135	30	4	5	1596	15	35	23
16	744	2.7	3600	2.7	1250	3850	412	230	145	33	5	6	1954	19	33	21
17	750	2.8	3700	2.8	1850	2800	423	210	155	35	6	7	1874	18	45	23
18	755	2.9	4000	2.9	1950	2200	485	205	175	39	7	8	1888	17	44	22
19	764	1.0	2000	1.0	1000	2100	431	207	210	41	8	9	1466	11	43	24
20	740	1.1	2400	1.1	1200	2000	456	234	145	44	9	3	1234	13	42	26
21	770	1.2	2600	1.2	1212	2600	423	210	177	43	3	4	1235	19	40	27
22	780	1.3	2650	1.3	1235	2500	321	211	198	12	4	2	1239	20	19	10
23	775	1.4	2780	1.4	1239	2450	212	109	123	17	2	3	1359	21	18	11
24	790	1.5	2800	1.5	1359	2350	455	209	145	16	3	4	1596	23	17	15
25	795	1.6	2850	1.6	1596	2250	333	246	164	15	4	5	1954	25	16	10

26	800	1.7	2855	1.7	1954	3200	345	245	164	14	5	6	1874	29	15	9
27	710	1.8	2900	1.8	1874	3250	325	244	188	10	6	7	1888	30	30	21
28	715	1.9	3050	1.9	1888	3290	544	350	178	9	7	8	1466	33	31	22
29	720	2.0	3055	2.0	1466	3300	555	461	195	8	8	9	1234	21	35	23
30	722	2.1	2950	2.1	1234	3333	556	329	200	7	9	3	1555	23	30	21
31	744	1.6	2705	1.9	2855	4025	852	310	185	11	6	7	1850	19	27	12
32	731	1.8	2754	1.7	2860	2860	544	320	174	13	7	8	1950	20	26	15
33	726	1.8	2807	1.8	1870	2910	546	244	45	19	8	9	1000	21	25	19
34	739	2.0	2904	2.2	1760	3065	455	155	144	20	9	3	1200	23	27	17
35	740	2.1	3005	2.3	1865	3070	455	144	122	21	3	4	1212	25	28	16
36	753	2.3	3509	2.5	1958	2955	744	454	123	23	4	2	1235	29	29	20
37	752	2.2	3101	2.6	2021	3335	488	234	110	25	2	3	1239	30	30	21
38	762	2.4	3306	2.4	2013	3355	443	299	122	29	3	4	1359	33	31	22
39	767	2.1	3501	2.5	1015	3877	566	328	135	30	4	5	1596	15	35	23
40	738	2.1	2900	2.1	1750	3050	450	150	144	20	9	3	1234	13	42	26
41	741	2.2	3000	2.2	1890	3055	444	145	122	21	3	4	1235	19	40	27
42	750	2.3	3500	2.3	1900	2950	750	450	123	23	4	2	1239	20	19	10
43	751	2.4	3100	2.4	2001	3330	486	230	110	25	2	3	1359	21	18	11
44	760	2.5	3300	2.5	2011	3350	444	290	122	29	3	4	1596	23	17	15
45	765	2.6	3500	2.6	1000	3800	564	320	135	30	4	5	1954	25	16	10
46	744	2.7	3600	2.7	1250	3850	412	230	145	33	5	6	1874	29	15	9
47	750	2.8	3700	2.8	1850	2800	423	210	155	35	6	7	1888	30	30	21
48	755	2.9	4000	2.9	1950	2200	485	205	175	39	7	8	1466	33	31	22
49	725	1.3	2200	1.3	2600	3300	555	135	200	15	2	3	2001	18	30	17
50	743	1.4	2300	1.4	2650	3500	666	145	201	19	3	4	2011	17	33	20

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